

Synthesis and characterization of co-precipitated magnesium-aluminium hydroxides hydrogel containing minor phosphate additive

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Coprecipitated Mg-Al hydroxides hydrogels in presence of minor phosphate additive were prepared in cold condition using different basic media viz. ammonium hydroxide and ammonium hydroxide-triethanolamine. DTA, TGA, particle size analyses and IR studies were performed for characterization of co-precipitates. Finer particle size was noticed for mixed hydroxides formed by using ammonium hydroxide-triethanolamine as basic medium. Co-precipitates were also subjected to thermal treatment at different temperatures and corresponding crystalline phases developed were identified by XRD analysis. Thermal treatment led to the dehydroxylation and subsequent collapse of structure of Mg-Al hydroxides hydrogel and ultimately to the formation of MgAl₂O₄ spinel phase at temperature as low as 600°.

Mg-Al double hydroxides were first synthesized by Feitnecht and Gerber¹. Later different parameters relating to preparation and characterization of Mg-Al based hydroxy compounds were studied by several workers with a view to ascertain the different optimum conditions^{2,3}. Some workers dealt with preparatory technique by using different precursors, basic media etc., while some others investigated structural changes during heating⁴⁻¹⁰. Finally efforts were being made for applicability of these materials in various fields¹¹⁻¹⁴.

In earlier communications Adhikari *et al.*¹⁵ showed that magnesium hydroxy phosphate prepared by coprecipitation technique when heat treated at different temperatures, magnesium oxide and magnesium phosphate were formed via amorphous phases. Itatani *et al.*^{16,17} observed that presence of minor amounts of phosphate accelerated the process of densification of MgO body due to the formation of minor liquid phase. In this paper an attempt has been made to synthesize and characterize Mg-Al based hydroxy compounds with minor amount of phosphates as additive using different basic media and applicability of these materials as potential binder for refractory production.

Results and discussion

After the formation of gel the mixed phases were allowed to age at RT for 24 h. In both cases due to presence of ex-

cess electrolyte in the medium the gelatinous mass settled at the bottom with separation of clear supernatant liquid. The physical texture of the gel was found to be more translucent in case of MAPB2 where NH₄OH-triethanolamine was used as basic media. pH of the mixed phase were measured in both cases (MAPB1, MAPB2) and were found to be 8.52 and 9.10 respectively. Higher value of pH exhibited by MAPB2 might be explained in terms of basicity. Triethanolamine was a stronger base than ammonia as the formation of 'onium ions' took place according to the following reaction : R₃N + H₂O ↔ R₃NH⁺ + OH⁻ (R ≡ C₂H₅O⁻). All the 'onium ions' in which nitrogen was quadricovalent unielectrovalent carry positive charge and were easily solvated in comparison with NH₄OH. Again as the number of bulky group (C₂H₅O⁻) increased, because of their +I effect, the lone pair became more available, increasing thereby, the basicity of the triethanolamine containing basic medium.

Average particle size of MAPB1 and MAPB2 coprecipitates were found to be 350.3 and 219.6 nm respectively. The smaller particle size of MAPB2 co-precipitate may be due to less agglomeration of the formed gel in presence of triethanolamine containing basic precipitating agent^{18,19}.

Typical XRD patterns of the co-precipitates dried at 110° and heat-treated at 400°, 480°, 600° and 1000° were shown

in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. The phases obtained were given in Table 1.

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of the co-precipitates dried at 110° and heat treated at 400, 480, 600 and 1000° (MAPB1).

In case of MAPB1 (110°) where NH₄OH was used as basic precipitating agent, monoclinic magnesium aluminium hydroxide [MgAl₂(OH)₈] phase predominates along with minor quantity of hydrotalcite [Mg₆Al₂CO₃(OH)₁₆.4H₂O]. But in case of MAPB2 (110°) where NH₄OH-TEA was used as precipitating agent the major phase was hydrotalcite with minor amount of hexagonal magnesium aluminium hydroxide [Mg₂Al(OH)₇]. So it may be concluded that NH₄OH favors the formation of hydroxide phase whereas NH₄OH-TEA medium dominated the formation of carbonated hydroxide phase. On heat treatment at 400° both the co-precipitates became amorphous due to collapse of their crystalline structure. Peaks of ill-defined spinel phases appeared at 480°. At 600° broad peaks of spinel phases appeared which became very sharp at 1000° indicating complete formation of spinel. However, the XRD pattern did not indicate the presence of phosphates in both the heat treated samples. This may be due to incorporation of negli-

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of the co-precipitates dried at 110° and heat treated at 400, 480, 600 and 1000° (MAPB2).

Table 1. Mineralogical phases of the co-precipitates at different temperatures

Temp. °C	MAPB1	MAPB2
110	MgAl ₂ (OH) ₈ (major) [monoclinic]	Mg ₆ Al ₂ CO ₃ (OH) ₁₆ .4H ₂ O (major) Mg ₂ Al(OH) ₇ (minor) [hexagonal]
400	Amorphous	Amorphous
480	Ill-defined spinel	Ill-defined spinel
600	Spinel (broad)	Spinel (broad)
1000	Spinel (sharp)	Spinel (sharp)

gible quantity of phosphates in both the samples.

In DTA curves, MAPB1 co-precipitate derived in NH₄OH medium showed two endothermic peaks at 142° and 296°. As reported in the literature^{10,20,21} the two endotherms were due to loss of free water and interlayer water respectively. The DTA curve of MAPB2 co-precipitate de-

rived in NH_4OH -TEA medium showed only one endotherm at 288° . Earlier studies had shown that at temperature lower than 300° , DTA curves of Mg-Al mixed hydroxide were always characterized by two endothermic peaks whereas in the same temperature range, the corresponding carbonated forms showed only one peak¹⁰. XRD analysis had shown that the co-precipitate (MAPB2) had hydrotalcite [$\text{Mg}_6\text{Al}_2\text{CO}_3(\text{OH})_{16}\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$] as the major phase whereas the other co-precipitate (MAPB1) did not have any carbonated form as a major phase. This clearly showed that the results of differential thermal analysis of the two co-precipitates were in good agreement with the observations of the earlier studies^{9,10,20-22}.

The TGA curves showed that the thermal decomposition can be divided into three steps¹⁰. Below 200° the loss was due to expulsion of adsorbed water and after the completion of this step, a sharp weight loss was noticed upto 450° . This was attributed to the elimination of structural water. In case of MAPB1, the maximum weight loss occurred around 400° while that was shifted to a higher temperature around 480° for MAPB2 probably due to structural differences between the two co-precipitates. The weight loss became minimum in the temperature range $480-650^\circ$. The process of weight loss almost ceased above 800° indicating the complete formation of spinel phase in the compound.

IR spectra of the samples (MAPB1 and MAPB2) dried at 110° and heated at 600° were recorded. In case of MAPB1 where NH_4OH was used as basic media a large number of peaks appeared due to the presence of PO_4^{3-} ions. In the composite structure some of these vibrations might be modified by the presence of other vibrations and some of them even disappeared. After dehydration at 600° , most of these vibrations disappeared. Only the OH^- stretching, bending and intermediate vibrations were observed. In case of MAPB2 dried at 110° where NH_4OH -TEA was used as precipitating agent, the dielectric constant of the medium altered and as a result a fewer number of bands appeared in the spectrogram. Some new bands appeared in the frequency range 2370 , 2334 and 2032 cm^{-1} . These bands appeared due to a complex interaction resulting from the restriction on the medium of the OH^- stretching and P-O stretching vibration. After heating at 600° , most of the bands disappeared except the OH^- stretching, bending and an intermediate couple vibration. So from an analysis of the IR spectra of the samples it was observed that there was distinct evidence of the influence of the following factors on the disposition, orientation, freedom and strength of the bands. The factors are (i) pH of the synthesis medium, (ii) dielectric constant of the medium and (iii) dehydration temperature and the extent of defect created in the structure.

In the present study, co-precipitates of magnesium aluminium hydroxy compounds containing minor amount of phosphates were prepared by co-precipitation technique using different basic precipitating agents. From the results of the study following conclusions can be drawn.

(i) Physical texture of the gel differed due to change in basic media.

(ii) The particle size of MAPB2 sample was finer to that of MAPB1 sample.

(iii) The hydroxide phase (major) in MAPB1 was monoclinic in nature whereas the hydroxide phase (minor) obtained in MAPB2 was hexagonal.

(iv) The major hydroxide phase found in the co-precipitate derived in NH_4OH medium was monoclinic magnesium aluminium hydroxide whereas major hydroxide phase in case of co-precipitate derived in NH_4OH -TEA medium was hydrotalcite.

(v) The noncarbonated hydroxide form (MAPB1) had two endothermic peaks whereas the carbonated form (MAPB2) of Mg-Al hydroxide had only one endothermic peak.

(vi) In both the cases spinel formation occurred at relatively low temperature and MAPB2 sample derived by NH_4OH -TEA as basic medium exhibited greater activity.

Experimental

Chemicals used for this investigation were magnesium chloride hexa hydrate ($\text{MgCl}_2\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), aluminium chloride hexa hydrate ($\text{AlCl}_3\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4 , 98% solution, specific gravity 1.75), ammonium hydroxide (NH_4OH , 25% solution, specific gravity 0.90), triethanolamine ($\text{CH}_2\text{OHCH}_2)_3\text{N}$ and all A.R. grade materials were taken. The co-precipitates of magnesium aluminium hydroxide hydrogel containing minor phosphate additives using ammonium hydroxide as basic medium and ammonium hydroxide-TEA as basic medium were termed as MAPB1 and MAPB2 respectively. The basic media used were (1) 20 wt% ammonium hydroxide solution and (2) 4 wt% ammonium hydroxide and 20 wt% triethanolamine solution. The resulted solutions showed the pH of 12.40 and 12.45 respectively. In presence of TEA a small amount NH_4OH (4 wt%) appeared sufficient to maintain the pH at desired level. Higher pH i.e. above 12.0 is selected for the maximum precipitation of Mg^{2+} . For incorporation of phosphate measured quantity of phosphoric acid was added to the salt solution in such a way that one litre salt solution contained 0.1 M MgO, 0.1 M Al_2O_3 and 0.001 M P_2O_5 . Finally the salt solution was added gradually with stirring to each of the basic medium in cold condition ($12 \pm 3^\circ$).

After complete addition of salt solution the pH was recorded. Co-precipitates thus obtained were allowed to stand for 24 h followed by filtration, washing with distilled water, drying at 110° and pulverization. Dried co-precipitates were subjected to heat treatment at different temperatures and the resultant phases were identified by X-ray diffraction with Ni-filtered CuK_α, 40 kV and 20 mA radiation. The thermal behavior of the co-precipitates were studied by differential thermal and thermogravimetric analyses using Shimadzu DT-50 apparatus with a heating rate of 10° per minute. The co-precipitates dried at 110° and heat treated at 600° were subjected to IR spectroscopic analysis using Jasco IR-700. Particle size of the coprecipitates dried at 110° was determined by Malvern Autosizer-2C equipment using laser beam.

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References

1. W. Feitknecht and M. Gerber, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1942, **25**, 131.
2. M. M. Mortland and M. C. Gastuche, *C. R. Acad. Sci. France*, 1962, **255**, 2131.
3. S. G. Mukherjee and B. N. Samaddar, *Trans. Ind. Ceram. Soc.*, 1966, **15**, 33.
4. R. Allmann, *Am. Miner.*, 1968, **53**, 1057.
5. R. J. Barton, *Am. Ceram. Soc. Bull.*, 1969, **48**, 759.
6. D. R. Messier and G. E. Gazza, *Am. Ceram. Soc. Bull.*, 1972, **51**, 692.
7. S. Miyata, *Clay and Clay Miner.*, 1975, **23**, 369.
8. T. Hattori and J. Mohri, *J. Ceram. Soc. Jpn.*, 1981, **89**, 287.
9. O. Yamaguchi, H. Taguchi, Y. Miyata, M. Yoshinaka and K. Shimizu, *Polyhedron*, 1987, **6**, 1587.
10. G. Gusmano, P. Nunziante, E. Traversa and G. Chiozzini, *J. Euro. Ceram. Soc.*, 1991, **7**, 31.
11. T. Ishobe, O. Matsumoto, S. Itose, F. Kawno, K. Saih, S. Takiuch and Y. Oda, *Taikabutsu Overseas*, 1995, **15**, 10.
12. M. Nakashima, T. Isobe, S. Itose, A. Touno and I. Shimizu, *Taikabutsu Overseas*, 1998, **18**, 60.
13. S. Yamaoka, R. Nakamura, T. Kaneshige, H. Sumimura and M. Namba, *Taikabutsu Overseas*, 1998, **18**, 79.
14. C. J. Ting and H. Y. Lu, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1999, **82**, 841.
15. U. B. Adhikari, S. K. Das and G. Banerjee, *Industrial Ceramics*, 1998, **18**, 12.
16. K. Itatani, K. Nishinaka, F. S. Howel, A. Kishioka and M. Kinoshita, *J. Ceram. Soc. Jpn.*, 1986, **94**, 801.
17. K. Itatani, K. Nishinaka, F. S. Howel, A. Kishioka and M. Kinoshita, *J. Ceram. Soc. Jpn.*, 1986, **94**, 807.
18. S. Hishita, Y. Yao and S. I. Shirasaki, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, 1989, **72**, 338.
19. M. E. V. Costa and J. L. Baptista, *J. Euro. Ceram. Soc.*, 1993, **11**, 275.
20. S. Miyata, *Clay and Clay Miner.*, 1980, **28**, 50.
21. G. Mascold and O. Marino, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1980, **35**, 93.
22. M. A. Ulibarri, C. Barriga and J. Cornejo, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1988, **135**, 231.